

The Economic Impact of International Tourists on the TRNC Economy

Huseyin Bozdoglar¹, Okechukwu Lawrence Emeagwali¹

¹*The American University, 99302, Cyprus (Northern)*

Abstract

This study set out to investigate the economic impact of the expenditure of international (non-turkish) tourists on the economy of North Cyprus. Using the input-output analytic process developed at the Michigan State University data spending data was retrieved from 460 respondents who made up the sample group. Findings as observable from the analysis and findings section revealed that 700,891 TL in additional direct sales were generated from international tourist expenditure, with every lira of international tourist spending generating 0.40kurus in additional direct income, especially to the primary tourism industry of the North Cyprus economy. The total additional sales generated also led to the direct creation of 19 additional jobs in the primary tourism industry.

Keywords: tourism, *economic impact analysis, multiplier analysis, North Cyprus*

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Introduction

This study is the first instalment of a two-part study on the economic impact of international tourist expenditure on the economy of North Cyprus. The pertinence of this two-part study is two-fold. The first being that there exists very few extant studies which have tried to observe the economic impact of international tourism exclusively, on the economy of Northern Cyprus. Secondly, where economic impact analysis had been carried out, it had mostly been limited to understanding the direct or primary impact on the primary tourism industry and none had focused on understanding the ripple effect of such primary impact on the secondary support industries in the form of indirect and induced impact on the economy of North Cyprus. Finally, a close examination of almost all of the extant literature on the economic impact of tourism have used methodologies which can be argued to be inappropriate to the adequate examination of such impacts. This study seeking to address these gaps in literature, focused on exclusively examining the impact of international tourists on the economy of North Cyprus especially from a spending or expenditure perspective. It also sought to provide a more holistic analysis of both the primary (direct) and secondary (indirect and induced) impact of such international tourists' spending on the primary tourism industry on the one hand and the ripple effect on the economy as a whole through its effects on supporting industries and salary and wage expenditures. Finally it embarked on this study using the most appropriate, traditional and widely accepted

methodological process referred to as the input-output analytic procedure. The input-output analytical framework and computational program used was adopted from one developed by the Michigan State University, with analytic values and figures reflecting those of Northern Cyprus. To better put the problem of the study in this first installation of the two-part study in perspective, the following research objective and research question was posed:

Research Objective 1: To understand the primary (direct) and secondary (indirect and induced) economic impact of international tourist expenditure on the economy of Northern Cyprus.

Research Question 1: What is the direct impact of the expenditure of international tourists on the economy of Northern Cyprus?

Review of Literature

This study begins the procedure of investigating this phenomenon by first of all reviewing literature with the aim of developing a theory-based hypothesis to be tested during the analysis phase. The ensuing paragraphs set out to thoroughly accomplish this. It begins by thoroughly scrutinizing the development and application of Economic Impact analysis in understanding the impact of Tourism on economies over the years. This includes a review of the literature on national and regional impacts especially paying attention to literature within both categories that have contributed significantly to the development of measurement parameters known to have shaped the degree to which measurement of the economic impact of this industry is possible.

A chronological rundown of salient points to be raised from the literature reviewed begins with a categorization of the body of relevant extant research into those which embody the *nascent unsophisticated* methods of economic impact estimation, and those which embodied the *present sophisticated* methods of economic impact estimation based on theoretically and empirically derived models such as the input-output model (James, 1999). A brief introduction to the input-output model is presented but expounded upon in separate part of the literature review as it is the estimation methodology of choice in this study.

The Nascent Unsophisticated Economic Impact Literature

As the category suggests, this initial section of the literature review explores, identifies and scrutinizes the earliest appearance of impact analysis literature, placing the review microscope on the early models that were developed and applied at the inception, presenting the review from a generic perspective rather than at the individual research work perspective (Yacob et al. 2007). This category of research which other scholars have termed naïve, is one characterized by a heavy dependence on customized methods or purported scientific approaches which are now been viewed as pseudo in nature (James, 1999). Moreover, Yacob et al. (2007) in their work, was also of the opinion that this early phase of the development of the research stream was characterized by studies which estimated the economic impacts of tourism using datasets which were largely incomplete or which by omission or commission left out crucial variables which would have led to more accurate or reliable results if included in the analytic models applied. Bonn, (2008) went further to demonstrate the

fact that conclusions on the impact of tourism or certain tourism activities on an economy drawn from such incomplete data were commonly fed to the public especially by political figures or responsible governmental agencies in order to account for, legitimize or justify certain tourism related budgetary expenditure or policies enacted. These justifications are made and such conclusions disseminated usually based on the assumption that the benefits of tourism is often obvious and substantial as it is only logical that with more influx of people to a tourism destination, increased levels of spending will occur, thus revenue volume will substantially increase, more and more locals will be gainfully employed, the influx and volume of foreign exchange will spike significantly, the volume of governmental revenue in form of tax would also rise, and therefore standard of living will generally improve (Bonn, 2008). Literature however revealed that approaching the study of the economic impact of tourism this way is however too simplistic and not realistic, as such a naïve approach often ignores the enormous costs associated with the development and provision of tourism related services which could be really substantial in volume (Moutinho, 2011).

Another visible feature of this nascent body of literature is that they are used to predict future trends in touristic activities and future touristic revenues expected without employing empirically tested methods of forecasting (James, 1999). Also, the naïve methods they use to study economic impact of tourism usually forms the premise upon which impromptu or intuitive decisions are taken relying on the prediction of future trends which are based on unsophisticated forecasting methods and incomplete datasets (Dwyer, et al., 2012).

In conclusion, the nascent body of literature which comprise studies that typically relied on unsophisticated methods of analysis, can thus be said to be a body of literature which draw their conclusions on the economic impact of tourism based almost entirely on observations drawn from datasets and sample populations which are very small and often biased in nature, and compounded by the lack of complete information upon which to make sound forecasts or judgments (Saayman et al., 2000).

In a bid to provide more accurate economic impact of tourism analysis and tourism related forecasts thereby increasing the reliability and validity of conclusions drawn from tourism research, other researchers set out to develop and employ more sophisticated techniques and methods. One of the earliest methods employed is the efficiency impact model also known as the cost benefit analysis- a method that seeks to weigh the cost of providing tourism related services against the benefits of doing so (James, 1999).

The Efficiency Impact Body of Literature

As mentioned in the preceding section, the first body of literature which sought to introduce a more systematic and empirical analytic method to the study of the economic impact of tourism rather than the methods employed by the nascent body of literature researchers, relied on the use of efficiency impact analytical tools, and the most prominent of these tools is cost-benefit analysis (Flecha, 2010). In general, this tool is one deployed by researchers to estimate the social implications by way of costs

to the society as well as benefits to the society of certain developmental projects whose investments the government or other concerned agencies are about to embark upon, with a view to arriving at strong conclusions which will more or less determine the decision of the concerned organizations to embark on the project or not (Dwyer, et al. 2012).

The cost benefit analysis tool was however first introduced into the study of tourism literature first as a means of determining whether the resources committed to the provision of touristic activities, would yield higher outcomes to the society if committed elsewhere perhaps in a different economic sector (James, 1999). In other words, the method sought to understand the efficiency of committing resources to the provision of tourism services against the provision of other services (Bonn, 2008). While this body of literature provided a more systematic approach to evaluating the impact of tourism activities, it is fraught with certain problems (Matias et al. 2009). One being that it is usually very difficult to accurately measure some individual observations seen as benefits or others seen as costs (Dwyer, et al. 2012). It is even more difficult to accurately place or interpret the actual value of the observed measurements. According to James, (1999) this is mostly due to the fact that the cost benefit analysis uses price estimates during the analytical process and there have been great criticisms from the scholarly body as to the reliability of findings drawn from a methodology that uses price estimates and embraces assumptions of perfect certainty in the marketplace as key analytic elements.

In the tourism literature, the sheer complexity of the deployment of the cost benefit analytic method has seen its very limited use in the economic impact research sub-stream (James, 1999). Vanhove (1983) revealed in his work, that cost benefit analytic methodology can be applied to the tourism research on four main dimensions or at four different levels of study viz: project, macro, public sector and individual tourist levels of study. Jamal & Robinson, (2009) however, revealed that the majority of cost benefit analysis literature deployed for the examination of tourism impacts were mostly restricted to the examination of the impact of individual tourist projects. The complexity of deploying the cost benefit analytic framework to the evaluation of the economic impact of tourism, is responsible for the very few and scarce existence of such studies in the economic impact of tourism literature, instead, a review of literature shows that there is an increase in the rate at which this method is used in evaluating the social and environmental impact of tourism (Bonn, 2008). This includes the works of James & Boer (1988) and Burns (1989) among others.

On the other hand, there has been an increase in the use of Multiplier analysis as opposed to cost benefit analysis in the examination of the economic impact of tourism (Saayman et al. 2000). This according to James (1999) is as a result of the fact that the multiplier analytic frameworks tend to present fewer data and analytic problems unlike the cost benefit analytic approach. In the second installation of this two-part study a succinct overview of how the use of multipliers in the estimation of the economic impact of tourism has developed over the years is presented.

Review of Tourism related Input-Output Literature

This sub section presents a review of literature pertaining to the development, evolution and adoption of the input-output analytic methodology in tourism research. Especially, as pertaining to their application in the estimation of the economic impact of tourism activities on the economy of towns, cities, states, nations and regions. It reviews this literature chronologically to show evolutionary trends of the application and incremental development of the input-output methodology as an economic impact assessment tool.

Early Studies (1966-1999)

On record as the earliest study to have deployed input-output analysis in the examination of the economic impact of tourism on economies is the work of Kalter, (1966). His work- a doctoral thesis, originally focused on the development and empirical testing of an effective method for estimating the impact of aqua-based recreational activities at the county level (Kalter, 1966). He applied Input-Output analysis as the preferred method for the estimation, with the sole purpose of highlighting how the methodology can be applied to tourism, the limitations likely to be encountered when adopting this methodology and how findings using this method can aid the decision making process especially with regard to public policy decisions (Lundberg 2011).

The second prominent study to have adopted the input-output methodology is the work of Strang, (1970). Also focused on recreational tourism, this work centered around the development of a static input-output model of Door County in Wisconsin-Madison, and was one of the few earliest studies to give a comprehensive description of the data collection process, the input-output transaction, multiplier and input coefficient tables. Using input-output analytic procedures, the author was able provide clear evidence that tourism impacted the Door County economy greatly in the short-term by contributing almost \$30 million yearly to the county's domestic economy (Surugui, 2009).

The work of Archer, (1977) constitutes the third in the series of prominent earliest studies to adopt or develop input-output analysis with regard to the tourism industry. However, within the body of literature on the economic impact on tourism, Archer, (1977) is perhaps one of the most cited research works especially pertaining to the development and application of multipliers in the study of the indirect and induced impacts of tourism on economies. Archer (1997)'s work which was based on the original work of W. Leontief was a deliberate effort to ensure the correct and accurate usage of multipliers in input-output models applied by researchers in the tourism field. Hence serving as a reference point for most of the subsequent studies which followed suit (Lundberg, 2011; Rushton et al 1999).

Further expanding the use of input-output analytic processes in the field of tourism, in 1982, Lichty& Steinnes carried out a three dimensional survey of businesses and their customers in the town of Ely in Minnesota. These surveys on the one hand focused on examining the over three hundred businesses in the town to ascertain the

objective of their existence and major income sources, on the other hand it focused on understanding from the perspective of the businesses, the ratio of resident and non-resident expenditure in each business and consequently aggregating the findings to determine the total expenditure of locals and foreigners (Pao, 2005). The third survey focused on the customers who patronized these businesses- in a bid to understand the perspective of the customers (domestic and foreign) regarding their estimated annual expenditure on Ely's businesses (Pao, 2005). The data collected from these surveys were then used to construct and input-output model of Ely's tourism industry. The model depicted the economic impact of tourism on Ely's economy estimated to be over \$4million (Pao, 2005).

The work of Liu &Turgut (1983) is widely believed to be one of the earliest studies to introduce the application of economic impact analysis in the field of tourism on a wide scale. More specifically, their work which focused on unraveling the economic impact of tourism in metropolitan Victoria, in the British Columbia province of Canada, was one of the earliest studies to introduce the work of Archer (1976) from the broader field of Economic Impact Analysis, to the multilayered aspect of the tourism field (Liu &Turgut, 1983). They adopted the regional input-output methodological framework developed by Archer (1976) as a means of analyzing the direct, indirect and induced impact of tourism on metropolitan Victoria. Income and employment constituted the economic variables for which impact were determined. As consistent with current body of literature, the authors, at a general level, were only able to derive a very low multiplier (0.65) for the income variable (Liu &Turgut, 1983). However on a more specific note tourists staying overnight in tourist facilities or attending overnight touristic events accounted for a much higher multiplier impact on income than any other category of tourists; while tourists on day trips accounted for an overall higher multiplier impact on the employment of residents than any other tourist categories. However, Lui&Turgut (1983) note that looking away from multiplier impacts and observing from an actual numbers perspective, tourists staying overnight accounted for the generation of approximately twenty-three more employment opportunities than tourists on day trips to the facilities in questions. In a bid to increase positive economic impact through tourism on metropolitan Victoria, the authors doled out a three point regulatory recommendation aimed solely at preventing touristic leakages from the economy of the region under study (Liu &Turgut, 1983).

Another prominent early study which impacted the development of input-output analysis as applicable to the tourism industry, is the work of Thompson et al. (1985). Unlike prior studies the authors tried to observe the regional economic impact of tourism activities not just on individual towns, but on an entire region (Thompson et al. 1985). They thus took as a case study, 17 casinos on native American reservations in Wisconsin (Thompson et al. 1985). In trying to include an understanding of the indirect and induced economic impact of the touristic activities, the authors conducted an input-output analysis using the multipliers contained within the Regional Input-Output Modeling System II (RIMS II) (Thompson et al. 1985). Although the study focused on understanding the economic impact of Casino patronage at the casinos under study on the economy of Winsconsin, it went even a step further to factor in the social impacts as well. Thus, while the authors discovered that gaming activities in the reservation brought Wisconsin a total of \$326.72 million (as at the time the study was

conducted, the negative social effects of the presence of compulsively addicted gamblers, and the cost of dealing with and caring for these addicts to the state, eventually reduced the economic contribution of these casinos to the Wisconsin economy to \$166.23 million (as at the time the study was conducted) or even a negative figure if higher social cost estimates are used (Thompson et al., 1985).

In 1989, in a bid to review how input-output analysis have been used in the tourism literature and more specifically in a bid to assess the usefulness of this analytic approach in the accurate assessment of the economic impact of tourism, Fletcher, (1989) carried out a comprehensive literature review of prior studies and was able to come to the conclusion that as at the time of authoring his paper, the tourism industry had no other alternative analytical procedure that could accurately and comprehensively examine and determine how tourism affects a nation's economy and the place of touristic activities in the economic structure of a nation. Fletcher (1989) however highlighted the limitations inherent in several assumptions made when using the input-output analytical procedure, and provided recommendations on how best to avoid those shortcomings. Perhaps of more tremendous use especially to researchers is a summary of all of the multipliers, that an input-output model generates, as well as recommendations on how best to interpret them (Fletcher 1989). Still in the spirit of examining the use of input-output economic impact analytic models in previous tourism studies, Fletcher teamed up with Archer in authoring a 1991 book chapter that focused on examining how input-output multipliers have been developed and applied over the years. Fletcher & Archer (1991) provided a vivid definition and description of the historical background of a multiplier, as well as the method with which they are applied in both input-output analytic model and other extant models.

The year 1991 was indeed a year in which the input-output analytical model was put under scrutiny as Briassoulis, (1991) joined the bandwagon in trying to understand how the I-O model had been applied in literature prior to 1991. He carried out a literature review of extant literature, and went ahead to reveal that while the input-output model offers a lot of advantages in understanding the economic impact of tourism to the economies of towns, states and regions, it also had very strong limitations as well (Briassoulis, 1991). Briassoulis, (1991) went further to categorize these limitations based on the issues they raised. These include issues associated with substantiating findings, issues associated with the aggregation of findings, issues associated with structural change within the industry as well as predictive issues and issues associated with the accurate measurement of the intangible impacts of tourism on an economy (Briassoulis, 1991). Using these categorizations, Briassoulis (1991) was able to offer recommendations on how the input-Output model could be further enhanced.

Revisiting the impact of casinos run by native American reservations on the economy of Wisconsin, Murray, (1993) sought to understand how the degree to which the economic impact of the gaming activities on the reservation have changed since Thompson et al. (1985) last studied the phenomenon. The difference between the Thompson et al. (1985) and Murray (1993) studies is that whereas Thompson et al. (1985) studied the economic impact of the gaming activities on Wisconsin's economy factoring in the social effect of the gaming activity itself on the overall economic impact ascertained, Murray's (1993) study focused solely on understanding the

economic impact of the gaming activities on the state's economy without concern for the social effect of addictive gaming on the overall economic impact observed. Murray (1993) applied the input-output analytic model in his research, collecting research data from participating native American tribes in Wisconsin. It concluded that native American gaming activities in the state of Wisconsin tremendously impacts Wisconsin's economy especially in the areas of income and employment (Murray 1993). Specifically as at the time of publishing, the author noted that gaming activities on the reservations provided a total of thirty two thousand jobs in Wisconsin, with ten thousand of those jobs generated within the gaming industry itself (Murray 1993). The also study noted that with regard to the native Indian community's economy, as at 1992, gaming activities generated a total of one hundred and thirty five million dollars for the native American reservation communities themselves (Murray 1993).

Examining the impact of tourism on small economies, Dinoto&Merk (1993) observed the economic impact of arts organizations in the US state of Idaho. Using a RIMS II regional input-output model, the study analyzed a set of data collected from the arts organizations and concluded that even though arts organizations generated approximately 38.5% (as at the time of authoring the study) of their revenue from foreign non-domestic sources, 56.7% of their total budgetary expenditure are expended domestically (Dinoto&Merk 1993). Through their study, Dinoto&Merk (1993) were able to conclude that another aspect of the economy that benefits from tourism is the public budget. They revealed that the state of Idaho will always receive a net cash gain from supporting arts organizations financially (Dinoto & Merk, 1995).

Another prominent early study on the economic impact of tourism and in which the input-output approach was also adopted is the work of Johnson (1993). In his work, Johnson (1993) tried to understand the technicalities inherent in the estimation of the regional economic impact of tourism activities. Specifically the economic impact of whitewater rafting on the upper Klamath river in the Oregon region of the USA was examined (Johnson 1993). Johnson (1993) sought to provide more precise, accurate and reliable estimates of the economic impact of the tour activity by considering in his analysis only expenditures expended in the region under study, identifying and considering the volume of multiple visits to the touristic destination under study and solely considering import substitute-related local expenditure. Here unlike prior studies, the author used the IMPLAN (Implementation Plan) input-output model (Johnson 1993). Again like prior studies, it focused on examining the impact of tourism on income and employment (Johnson 1993). Findings revealed that models which were sophisticated enough to account for the substitution of imports by both domestic and foreign tourists embarking on multiple visits to a particular tour destination (and who have a high tendency to have engaged in recreational touristic activities during their visits) would yield lesser impact parameters than those models which paid no attention to the inherent impact of multiple visits and domestic substitution (Johnson 1993).

In a bid to exhibit the power of input-output analytic models to present a more accurate representation of the effect of tourism activities on an economy, Finn & Erdem (1995) challenged the findings of a study carried out by the West Edmonton Mall, in which the Mall authorities estimated that the Mall had in 1986 added about

forty thousand jobs to the local economy and generated over seven hundred million dollars through a total of nine million visitors who patronized it in the same year. Finn & Erdem (1995), were able to show that the methodology used by the Mall authorities were flawed and applying an input-output model, they proved that real probability sampling techniques (inherent in the input-output model) were superior to the judgment sampling used by the Mall authorities. They also claimed that the input-output model controlled for the ‘differential time spent’, “intercept response rates” and used “incremental effects’ rather than total effects. Something the Mall authorities failed to control for in their studies (Finn & Erdem 1995 p. 5). After applying input-output analytic procedures, the authors were able to provide more accurate estimates, adjusting the findings of the impact of the Mall on the economy to the provision of about thirteen thousand eight hundred jobs, the generation of one hundred and seventeen million in household income through five million visitors who visited the mall in the year under review (Finn & Erdem 1995).

Recent Studies (2000- Present)

More recently however, some key research work have contributed to the way in which economic impact studies are conducted. Among the list of prominent research work which have shaped economic impact analysis studies recently includes the work of Gelen, (2003) in which he studied the characteristics of the economic impact of the 1999 British Open on the local economy. The study revealed a very small impact of total visitor expenditure on additional income generated. According to the authors the small multiplier effect recorded was a testament to the very rigorous and painstaking methodological approach which minimized exaggeration of the secondary impact of the tourist spending recorded. This methodological approach had earlier on been used by Crompton et al. (2001) as well as by Tyrell & Johnston (2001).

Another study which has made significant contributions to the recent to the recent economic impact analysis methodological approach is the work of Chhabra et al. (2003), in which the authors sought to understand the economic impact of visitor spending on several Scottish festivals organized by residents of the rural areas of North Carolina in the states, using input-output analysis as the analytical framework of choice. Findings from their studies revealed that although the primary tourism industry which caters directly to the tourists benefitted from heavy spending by the tourist who visited, secondary support industries on the other hand were not equally impacted as the multiplier effects observed yielded very small estimates. The authors note that from a direct impact perspective, the economic sector which benefitted the most depended on the number of nights the tourists spent during the festivities. It noted that for multiple day festivals, the lodging and accommodation sector benefitted the most from direct spending. However, for single day festivals, the food and beverage sector benefitted the most. Due to the very small secondary impact of visitor spending, the authors note that the overall contributions of the Scottish festivals to the local economy was negligible compared to other sources of economic activity within the regions studies. Finally, the 2005 work of Lee & Taylor shows the application of the economic impact analysis of a mega event (the 2002 world cup) on the economy of South Korea. The methodology employed was exclusive in nature to only visitors

who visited the country solely to watch the games. Findings showed that international visitors attracted by the games spent far more than visitors on vacation or other touristic reasons. Other studies reinforced the use of the input-output analysis but for time and space all of them will not be discussed here. However, the following section will focus more on understanding the application of the input output method on economic impact of tourism related studies conducted in the North Cyprus region.

Input-Output Analytic Model in Tourism Impact studies in North Cyprus.

Recognized solely by the republic of Turkey, Northern Cyprus is a self-declared nation state autonomous from the republic of Cyprus (katircioğlu 2007). The division of the island of Cyprus since 1974 has literally seen the south of Cyprus gain legitimacy among the international community and admittance into the European Union, while the north also referred to as the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus has been sidelined on the international scene (katircioğlu 2007). Despite the minimal recognition it has received globally since 1974, several economic sectors such as the higher education, tourism and banking sectors have received considerable attention from the international community (katircioğlu 2007). Having only limited trading opportunities with other nations, often carried out through Turkish land, sea and air ports; the tourism and education sectors have constantly been used to shore up trade deficits with trading partners as historical records from 1975 contained in the TRNC State Planning Organization (SPO) database reveals (katircioğlu, et al, 2007). Seeing then that tourism constitutes a major economic sector in North Cyprus, has there been any study which aimed to effectively understand the actual primary and secondary economic impact of international tourism on the broader economy of North Cyprus? A review of extant literature does reveal that the bulk of empirical studies on tourism activities in North Cyprus are composed of the prominent works of katircioğlu (2007), which using SPO data from 1977 to 2003 examined the tourism led growth of North Cyprus' economy within the period under study. While the findings of this particular study were inconclusive, subsequent studies by the same author focusing on estimating the combined effect of international tourism and higher education (the independent variables) on the economic growth (the dependent variable) of North Cyprus (katircioğlu, 2007). Again, using the long-run equilibrium relationship between the independent and dependent variables as a determining factor, findings confirmed a combined tourism and education led growth of the North Cyprus economy within the period under study (katircioğlu, 2007). Other prominent studies focused on applying econometric models to forecasting the demand for tourism, the growth of tourism and the socio-economic effects of tourism (katircioğlu, 2006, 2013 & 2011); as well as an estimation of casino gambling tourism (Alipour, 2010) and a host of others.

Despite the wealth of studies available, there has not been any study which categorically focused on understanding how international tourism actually affects the economy of Northern Cyprus from a primary (direct) and secondary (indirect and induced) impact perspective. Secondly, there has been no extant study which sought to examine this phenomenon in North Cyprus using the widely respected and

historically traditional input-output model as well as its traditional use of multipliers in the estimation of secondary impacts.

The purpose of this study therefore is to present a deeper examination of this phenomenon using the most appropriate and up-to-date and preferred method (input-output) thereby providing quantifiable evidence of the presence, lack of and nature of economic impact exerted by international tourism on the economy of North Cyprus. Especially from a Jobs and income perspective and as related to the direct and indirect industries involved. From the wealth of information gleaned from the review of literature carried out in this section, the following hypothesis were developed to be tested in the analysis section of this study.

H₁: Every Lira increase in international tourist expenditure will impact the tourism industry (direct) positively increasing the amount of income and jobs generated within the industry.

H₀: Every Lira increase in international tourist expenditure will have no direct impact on the tourism industry and no impact on the amount of income and jobs generated within the industry.

Methodology and Findings

This study aimed to understand the impact of international tourism on the economy of Northern Cyprus, by analyzing spending data retrieved from inbound and outbound tourists from countries other than the TRNC and Turkey. The Input-Output Economic Impact analytical method was employed as is the custom with Economic Impact of tourism analysis literature. An EIA of tourism programmed excel-based spreadsheet was used for the computation of direct and indirect effects.

This spreadsheet was adopted from the Tourism department of Michigan State University. A random sample of 460 tourists were administered a spending survey instrument adopted from Stynes, (1999) and the spending and duration of visit data retrieved was inputted into the EIA excel spreadsheet program and effects computed accordingly. The analytic process began with the analysis of individual visitor spending per day, followed by a computation of the total spending carried out by all of the constituents of the chosen sample. In the third step, margins related to the spending criteria were identified from secondary sources to ensure that only spending accruable to the TRNC economy was included in the study and leakages were exempted from the study. Once the margins were identified, the next step involved the determination of the direct impact of the total spending observed on the primary tourism sector.

The next step is the determination of multipliers and economic ratios for the TRNC region and this was done through the use of secondary data contained the TRNC SPO database. The final phase of the analysis involves the application of the multiplier to the direct effects observed to obtain a value of the total impact of the touristic spending on the TRNC economy. From which a simple deduction of the direct impact from the total impact observed, reveals the indirect or secondary effects of

international tourism on the economy of Northern Cyprus. This process is explained in more detail in the ensuing paragraphs.

Analysis of Expenditures Per Visitor Per Day

As mentioned in the methodology section, and as recommended by economic impact analysis scholars (such as Stynes, 1999), to accurately analyze the spending carried out by international tourists visiting Northern Cyprus from countries other than the TRNC and Turkey, it is first of all important to understand the average number of visitors of this description who visited Northern Cyprus in the year under study.

Records from the SPO database and official statements made by the chairman of the Turkish Cypriot Tourism and Travel Agencies Union, Mr. Orhan Tolun that by the second quarter of 2014, the annual volume of tourists that visited the TRNC rose to 760,000 with about 500,000 tourists originating from Turkey and approximately 65,000 from the UK and 30,000 from Germany (HRI, 2014). In other words, a total of 260,000 tourists originating from countries other than the TRNC and Turkey were recorded. As mentioned earlier in the methodology section, the chosen sample of 460 respondents was thus accurately representative of the tourist population under study. Table 1 below presents the average spending information for each of the international tourist surveyed.

Table 1: Spending per visitor per day

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Spending Category	Day Users	Overnight Stays
Lodging	0TL	120TL
Restaurant	42TL	90TL
Groceries	20TL	32TL
Gas & Oil	63TL	21TL
Recreation	8TL	30TL
<u>Other</u>	<u>54TL</u>	<u>31TL</u>
Total	187TL	324TL
	Day Users	Overnight Stays
Number of Visitor days	97	2.548

Bearing in mind that the sample chosen for this study had been proven to be accurately representative of the particular category of tourist population (International tourists) under study, the finding from the analysis of responses from the sample studies can thus be extrapolated to represent and mirror a similar effect for the actual population. Thus Table 1 above attempting to understand the average spending carried out by individual tourists under the category being studied used information retrieved from the 460 survey respondents.

From the table and from the sample population perspective, it can be seen that in the past touristic year, Northern Cyprus attracted a total of 97 day visitors and approximately 363 overnight visitors who stayed in the country for an average of seven nights. Thus translating this information into visitor days by day users and visitor nights by overnight tourists, it can be observed that from the sample population perspective there was a record of 97 day visits and 2,548 visitor nights (363*7). The survey instrument further revealed as highlighted by Table 1 above that since day visitors are visitors who do not spend a night in the TRNC, the average day visitor recorded no average spending on lodging or accommodation facilities such as hotels, motels or hostels, while overnight visitors spent on the average 120TL on lodging and accommodation. All in all day visitors of international extraction were recorded to spend approximately 187TL per day on the average, while overnight tourists of the same extraction spent on the average, 324TL per night as illustrated in the Table above. As mentioned earlier on in the methodology section, categorizing the spending activities into the different categories makes it a lot easier to observe how spending impacts different economic sectors and also makes it easy to apply margins to the goods sold in the region to determine the average capture rate of revenues accruing from such sales in the TRNC. Once the average spending per day and night visitors was determined the next step involved the determination of the total spending carried out by the sample group in the TRNC within the period under study.

Analysis of Total Expenditure by Visitors

Table 2 below shows the total spending recorded for all of the visitors within the study sample. These values were computed by multiplying the average amount spent per day or night by day and overnight international tourists by the total number of day and overnight tourists in the study sample. From Table 2 it can be seen that the visitors in the sample group spent a gross total of 843,691TL in the TRNC during their visit.

Table 2: Total spending by visitors

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Spending Category	Day Users	Overnight Stays	Total
Lodging	-	305.760	305.760
Restaurant	4.074	229.320	233.394
Groceries	1.940	81.536	83.476
Gas & Oil	6.111	53.508	59.619
Recreation	776	76.440	77.216
<u>Other</u>	<u>5.238</u>	<u>78.988</u>	<u>84.226</u>
Total	18.139	825.552	843.691

From the table it can be seen that spending by day visitors account for 2.15% of the total international tourist spending while spending by overnight international tourists account for 97.85% of the total spending by international tourists in the TRNC.

While Table 2 presents us with an idea of the total amount spent by respondents within the study group in the TRNC region, it does not tell us the proportion of this total amount retained or captured within the local economy. In other words the amount includes monies captured within the local TRNC economy as well as leakages that flow to other regions especially as a result of goods and services sold in the TRNC but not produced there. The next phase of the analysis involves the determination of margins representative of the percentage of the amount spent on a particular good or service that was retained within the TRNC economy.

Margin Determination

Table 3 below presents the average margin made on products and services offered in mostly the primary tourism industry as gleaned from secondary data available from the SPO database. It can be seen that for the recreational, lodging and restaurants sector, a 100% capture rate is observed for the region. This is because most of these facilities located within the region are owned and operated by local residents of the TRNC.

Table 3: Margins

Table 3. Margins

Spending category	Margin	Local Prod	Imports
Lodging	0%	100%	0%
Restaurant	0%	100%	0%
Groceries	20%	10%	70%
Gas & Oil	15%	0%	85%
Recreation	0%	100%	0%
Other	50%	10%	40%

However, the table shows that all other economic sectors such as the grocery retail sector, the gas and oil (Transportation) sector and other sectors, captured only a combination of the gross margins and the share of production that was carried out in Northern Cyprus. Applying these margins to the total sales recorded in each sector as presented in Table 3 allows one to observe the direct effect of spending carried out by the international tourists on the primary tourism industry as presented in the ensuing section.

Analyses of the Direct Impact of Total Expenditure on Local Production

In Table 4 below, a representation of the application of the margins compiled in table 3 to the total sales recorded for each of the sectors in Table 3 to arrive at a computation of the direct impact of international tourist spending on the Northern Cyprus Economy is presented.

Table 4: Computation of direct effects

Table 4. Computation of Direct Effects

Sector	Local Prod	Retail Margin	Import	Total	Pct Local
Lodging	305.760	-	-	305.760	100%
Restaurant	233.394	-	-	233.394	100%
Grocery production	8.348	16.695	58.433	83.476	30%
Gas & Oil refining	-	8.943	50.676	59.619	15%
Recreation	77.216	-	-	77.216	100%
Other manf.	8.423	42.113	33.690	84.226	60%
<u>Retail Trade</u>	<u>67.751</u>				
Total	700.891	67.751	142.800	843.691	83%

The table shows that for the recreation, restaurant, lodging and accommodation industry there were no leakages through imports neither was there a need to record any margins as all of the revenue from these sectors were completely captured within the Turkish Cypriot economy. This is due to the fact that almost all of the businesses which provided recreational, accommodation and restaurant services were residents of Northern Cyprus, in other words, these services were produced by the local economy using local factors of production. However applying the 20% margin which grocery retailers and wholesalers earned from the sale and distribution of grocery products to the spending figures recorded for the international tourist included in the study group, reveals that out of the 83,476 Turkish Lira the respondents spent on groceries, 70% (58,433 TL) of the total revenue was lost through import leakages flowing back to the manufacturers or producers of the products located outside of Northern Cyprus. 10% (8,348 TL) and 20% (16,695 TL) of the revenue were captured within the TRNC economy as accruals from local production activities and retail/wholesale margin respectively.

With regard to total 59,619 TL revenue recorded in the Gas, Oil and other transportation related expenditure, a leakage of 85% (50,676 TL) attributed to the fact that most of these products are imported from Turkey. Only 15% of the total revenue (8,943 TL) was captured and retained within the TRNC economy in form of margins derived from the resale of these products and provision of other services related to these products. Other products and service sectors recorded a total of 84,226 TL out of which an average of 50% and 10% were captured in the North Cyprus economy in

form of margins from resale and income from local production respectively. Also other products such as souvenirs, artifacts as well as local services such as folklore displays and performances produced locally accounted for a total of about 67,751 TL all captured within the local economy in the form local production revenues.

All in all the direct impact of the spending carried out by the international tourists within the sample group reveals that of the grand total 843,691 TL revenue generated by the tourists, 83% (768,642 TL) was captured and retained within the primary tourism sector of the TRNC economy.

To understand the indirect and induced (secondary) impact of the total spending recorded for the international tourists who participated in the study, it is important to establish and apply multipliers to the spending figure as recommended in extant literature (Bonn, 2008; Dwyer, et al. 2012; & Stynes, 1999). The second installation of this two-part study will present an analysis of the multipliers and economic ratios used in this study.

Application of Multipliers and Economic Ratios for North Cyprus

Applying the formulas mentioned in the methodology section of this study, to economic data retrieved from the SPO database, the following multipliers and economic ratios in Table 5 were determined for the TRNC economy for 2013.

Table 5: Multipliers and economic ratios for North Cyprus

Table 5. Multipliers & Ratios for North Cyprus (From an I-O model)

Sector	Direct effect ratios			Total effect multipliers		
	Income/Sales	Jobs/\$MM Sales	Sales I	Sales II	Income II/ Sales	Jobs II/ Sales
Lodging	0,34	23,0	1,40	1,70	0,60	33
Restaurant	0,35	31,0	1,38	1,66	0,57	39
Grocery production	0,15	5,3	1,37	1,54	0,34	12
Gas & Oil refining	0,05	0,6	1,30	1,38	0,14	4
Recreation	0,35	31,0	1,35	1,65	0,60	40
Other manf.	0,26	9,0	1,32	1,56	0,46	16
Retail	0,51	28,0	1,17	1,52	0,70	35
Tourism multiplier (calculated)	0,36	26,6		1,67	0,59	36

Computation of Total Economic Impact (Direct, Indirect and Induced) on Sales Income and Jobs in North Cyprus.

The multipliers and economic ratios listed in Table 5, were then applied to the section of the direct effects table in Table 4 which shows the proportion of sales accruable to the local Northern Cyprus economy in other words, the ‘local production’ column. This application was made in order to determine the value of total sales, total income and total employment economic impact of spending carried out by international tourists. Table 6 below presents a succinct representation of the direct impact computations.

Table 6: Spending impacts

Table 6. Spending Impacts

Sector	Direct Effects			Total Effects		
	Sales	Income	Jobs	Sales	Income	Jobs
Lodging	305.760	103.958	7,0	519.792	183.456	10,1
Restaurant	233.394	81.688	7,2	387.434	133.035	9,1
Grocery production	8.348	1.252	0,0	12.855	2.838	0,1
Gas & Oil refining	-	-	0,0	-	-	0,0
Recreation	77.216	27.026	2,4	127.406	46.330	3,1
Other manf.	8.423	2.190	0,1	13.139	3.874	0,1
<u>Retail</u>	<u>67.751</u>	<u>34.553</u>	<u>1,9</u>	<u>102.982</u>	<u>47.426</u>	<u>2,4</u>
Total	700.891	250.667	18,7	1.163.609	416.958	24,9

Direct impact

In Table 6 above it can be observed that the direct impact of tourist spending was first computed by applying the economic ratios in Table 5 to the direct sales recorded in Table 4. For the lodging sector, it can be seen from a direct impact perspective that direct sales in that sector amounted to a total of 305,760 TL. When the income/sales economic ratio was applied ($0.34 * 305,760$ TL) the total direct sales led to the generation of 103,958 TL in personal income; and when the jobs/sales economic ratio was applied ($23j/mm * 305,760$ TL) it lead to the generation of about 7 jobs.

For the restaurant sector, direct sales amounted to a total of 223,394 TL. When the income/sales economic ratio was applied ($0.35 * 223,394$ TL), it directly impacted income by generating a total of 81,688 TL in personal income. Also when the job/sales economic ratio was applied ($31j/mm * 223,394$ TL), it directly impacted jobs in the primary tourism sector by generating about 7.2 jobs.

Again with the groceries sector of the primary tourism market a total sales of 8,348 TL was recorded as local production, and upon the application of the income/sales ratio ($0.15 * 8,348 \text{ TL}$) personal income directly generated was computed to be about 1,252 TL. Upon the application of the jobs/sales economic ratio, ($5.3j/mm * 8,348 \text{ TL}$) it was also computed to have generated no additional job.

With regard to the direct impact of tourist spending in the oil and gas sector of the primary tourism market, it was observed that the sector generated no revenue captured within the local economy under the auspices of 'local production' as all of the products were imported.

With regard to the recreation industry of the primary tourism market on the other hand, total sales accruable to the local production section completely captured within the local economy was recorded in Table 4 as 77,216 TL. When the income/sales economic ratio is applied ($0.35 * 77,216 \text{ TL}$) it generated a total of 27,026 TL in personal income; and when the jobs/sales economic ratio was applied, ($31j/mm * 77,216 \text{ TL}$) it was recorded to generate a total of about 2.4 additional jobs.

Again with regard to the direct impact of tourist spending on the manufacturing sector within the primary tourism market it was recorded in Table 4, that total manufacturing sales related with tourist spending was 8,423 TL. And upon application of the income/sales and job/sales economic ratios yielded a total of 2,190 TL in additional personal income and about 1 additional job in that sector.

Finally with regard to the total direct sales recorded for the retail sector (67,751 TL) it was recorded that a total of 34,553 TL of additional personal income was generated, while about 2 new additional jobs were created within the retail sector.

In summary the total direct impact of the tourist spending recorded for the respondents within the sample group chosen for this study on the primary tourism industry catering directly to the international tourists was the generation of a total of 700,891 TL in direct sales, 250,667 TL in additional personal income and a total of approximately 19 additional jobs in the primary tourism sector. Thus for every Turkish Lira spent by international tourists visiting North Cyprus, yielded 0.40Kurus in additional personal income.

Total Impact

The last three columns of Table 6 represents the total impact of expenditure carried out by the international tourists who make up the chosen sample group of this study. It was obtained by applying multipliers for the TRNC region listed in Table 5 to the value of direct sales recorded for each sector as done with economic ratios during the determination of direct impact in the preceding direct impact section. To estimate the total direct, induced and indirect impact of international tourists' spending on the lodging and accommodation sector of the Northern Cyprus economy, the total impact multiplier on sales (1.70) was applied to the total direct sales generated for that sector (305,760 TL) by computing ($305,760 \text{ TL} * 1.70$) this yielded a total of 519,792 TL in total (direct, indirect and induced) sales in the economy. Also the application of the income/sales multiplier to the same lodging sector ($305,760 \text{ TL} * 0.60$) yielded a total of 183,456 TL in total income in the economy. Finally the application of the job/sales

multiplier (305,760 TL * 33j/mm) yielded a total of 10.1 additional jobs to the economy.

With regard to the restaurant sector, the total impact of tourist spending was computed by multiplying the total sales (233,394 TL) by the sales multiplier (1.66) which yielded total sales of 387,434 TL for the restaurant sector. Total additional income and jobs created within the restaurant industry were derived by multiplying the total direct sales generated (233,394 TL) by the income/sales (0.57) and the job/sales (39 j/mm) multipliers respectively. This showed that a total additional income of 133,035TL and 9.1 jobs were generated and added to the North Cyprus economy by restaurants as a result of international tourist spending in the year under review.

With regard to the total impact of the international tourist expenditure on the groceries industry, computations were made by multiplying the direct sales generated by local production within the sector (8,348 TL) by the sales (1.54), income (0.34) and jobs (12 j/mm) multipliers. This computation revealed that international tourist expenditure on the groceries industry generated a total of 12,855 TL in additional sales, 2,838 TL in additional income and approximately 1 new job to the Northern Cyprus economy.

Due to the fact that no local production activity was carried out within the North Cyprus region in the oil and gas sector, no computation was carried out on the direct out total impact of this sector on the northern Cyprus economy, due to the fact that most of the products were imported.

Again with regard to the total expenditure carried out by international tourists within the Northern Cyprus recreation industry, the direct sales generated by the sector (77,216 TL) was multiplied by the sales (1.65), income (0.60) and job (40j/mm) multipliers respectively. This was observed to yield a total of 127,406 TL in additional sales, 46,330 TL in additional personal income and about 3 additional jobs in the recreation industry of North Cyprus. Also, with regard to the total impact of international tourist spending on the manufacturing sector, it is important to recall the direct sales generated by expenditure made by the sample group under study. A direct sales of 8,423 TL was recorded for the sector and when multiplied by the sales (1.56), income (0.46) and job (16j/mm) multipliers respectively, it yielded a total impact of 13,139 TL in total sales, 3,874 TL in additional income and about 1 additional job in the sector.

Finally, with regard to the total impact of international tourists' spending on the retail industry, the direct sales recorded for the sector (67,751 TL) was multiplied by the sales (1.52), income (0.70) and job (35j/mm) multipliers respectively, and this yielded a total impact of 102,982 in total sales for this sector, 47,426 TL in total additional income in the sector and a total of about 3 new additional jobs in the retail sector.

In summary, the total expenditure by the international tourists within the chosen sample of 460 respondents used in this study had a total impact on the economy of Northern Cyprus in terms of total additional sales generated, total additional personal income generated and total number of jobs created. All in all, as can be seen from Table 6, the tourist spending generated a total of 1,163,609 TL of additional sales to the economy, served as a source of additional personal income to residents to the tune of 416,958 TL and a total of about 25 new jobs to residents of Northern Cyprus.

Summary of the Analysis and Findings

This section presented details of the analytic process applied. A total of 460 international tourists from countries other than Turkey and North Cyprus participated in the study. These participants who were randomly selected constituted the sample size which was scientifically chosen to accurately represent the total population (260,000) of international tourists originating from such countries, according to the KITSAB. These 460 tourists were made up of day visitors and overnight staying tourists. All in all a total of 97 day visits were recorded while with an average of 7 nights per visitor, a total of 2548 overnight stays were recorded. In other words of the international tourists to visit North Cyprus, 3.7% of them were day visitors, while 96.3% of them were overnight staying visitors. An analysis of the spending survey instrument administered revealed that the average day visitor spent about 187 TL per day, while an average overnight staying international tourist, spent about 324 TL per night, with a sizeable chunk of that spent on lodging and accommodation. Total visitor spending was recorded to be 843,691 TL with overnight visitors accounting for 97.85% of the overall spending (see Table 6 above). North Cyprus' economy captures about 83% of this spending or about 768,642 TL as total direct sales.

From a primary (direct) impact perspective, the economic sector benefitting the most from the direct sales listed above is the lodging and accommodation sector (305,760 TL), restaurants sector (233,394 TL), the retail sector (67,751 TL) and the recreation sector (77,216 TL). These direct sales produced 250,667 TL in direct personal income constituting worker salary and wages creating 19 additional jobs in the primary tourism industry in the process (Table 10).

From a total impact perspective facilitated through the use of multipliers and economic ratios for the North Cyprus region, the total impact of international tourists' spending on Northern Cyprus is the 1,163,609 TL in additional sales, 416,958 TL in additional income generated and about 25 new jobs created within the larger Northern Cyprus economy.

Summary

Having presented the impetus for carrying out the study in the preceding chapter and the major concerns and focal areas of the study it is important to also reiterate and call to mind the major research objective, research questions and hypothesis developed to guide this study. To guide the study, the following research question was set: **Research Question 1:** What is the direct impact of the expenditure of international tourists on the economy of Northern Cyprus?

Also, to effectively achieve the second objective, a thorough review and analysis of previous literature was carried out which led to the decision to adopt the input-output analytical framework developed at the University of Michigan. The model was chosen for two reasons. The first being that it was a regional economic impact model and two it was the only model that provided an accompanying Excel based program, making it

easy to adopt from a computational perspective. Finally, in response to the research question posed, and after a thorough review of literature, the following hypothesis was postulated:

H₁: Every Lira increase in international tourist expenditure will impact the tourism industry (direct) positively increasing the amount of income and jobs generated within the industry.

H₀: Every Lira increase in international tourist expenditure will have no direct impact on the tourism industry and no impact on the amount of income and jobs generated within the industry.

Findings from this study as observable from the analysis and findings section revealed that 700,891 TL in additional direct sales were generated by international tourist expenditure, with every lira of international tourist spending generating 0.40kurus in additional direct income, especially to the primary Tourism industry; of the Northern Cyprus economy. The total additional sales generated also led to the direct creation of 19 additional jobs in the primary tourism industry. The findings above, thus demands that the null hypothesis be rejected.

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